
A Study on Siddhi Tribes of Yallapura Village in Uttara Kannada District

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Abstract

While Siddhis came into India they procured various positions in accordance with their abilities and luck. Thus the researcher observes various streams of Siddhis the first one being those employed as soldiers, as bodyguards, as guards for kings harem and as generals leading the army at battles. This section of Siddhis did enjoy a better status in the society both in the eyes of the citizens and the royalty as well. They did enjoy security, were treated with respect, better fed in order to keep them fit for the future battles and to preserve law and order in the kingdom. Some of the Siddhis won the hearts of their kings and queens to an extent that they were given gifts both in the form of land grants and gold. The second stream of Siddhis was those employed in the houses, fields and other domestic sectors. Pinto reveals to us that the prestige of Portuguese in Goa in the 16th century was measured according to the number of slaves each possessed. Though many slaves served a single household Siddhis must have not had much to converse with each other as they were not of the same tribe and kinship. The third stream of Siddhis are those bought by the local Bhattas, Muslim land lords and the Christian land owners sold by the Portuguese. There is a 50,000 strong Siddi population across India of which more than a third live in Karnataka. Siddis mainly speak the Kannada language, which belongs to the Dravidian family. Some also speak other languages, such as Konkani and marathi. The Siddi, also known as Siddhi, Sheedi, or Habshi, do an ethnic group inhabit India and The Siddi community is currently estimated at around 50,000–60,000 individuals, with Karnataka, Gujarat and Hyderabad in India and Makran and Karachi in Pakistan as the main population centres.

Keywords: Siddhi tribes, Community, Situation, Problems, customs and tradition.

1. INTRODUCTION

The decay of social status as hard working and independent tribe and then presents how social formation of Siddhis is being shaped in the modern times by presenting the influence of caste system among Hindu Siddhis, their change of names from those of Africans to Portuguese and Indian, their exploitation and various myths people have about Siddhis. The researcher also describes their social set up in which he presents their divine kingship, marital status, food habits, health, medicine, language, sports and religion. There are various hypotheses on the origin of the name *Siddi*. One theory is that the word was a term of respect in North Africa, similar to the word *sahib* in modern India and Pakistan. A second theory is that the term *Siddi* is derived from the title borne by the captains of the Arab vessels that first brought Siddi settlers to India. These captains were known as *Sayyid*. The majority of the Siddhis in Karnataka are descended from Bantu peoples from Southeast Africa that were brought to the Indian subcontinent as slaves by the Portuguese between the 16th and 19th centuries. During the Goan Inquisition, some of these slaves were freed and some escaped into the forests of the neighbouring Karnataka state. As the bulk of the Inquisition's records are now destroyed, a thorough reconstruction of the Siddhis' history in India and in Karnataka is very difficult. However, the few records that exist present a picture of oppression and ill treatment that the slaves were subjected to.

SOCIO CULTURAL SITUATION OF SIDDHI TRIBES

Religion: The one factor which binds the Siddhis, irrespective of their religion is the *Hiriyaru* or ancestor worship. The dead are believed to be nearby, in the form of spirits. They are regarded as witnesses to be consulted by a family in all its concerns. On occasions like births, marriages and deaths, the ancestors are invoked. The home is organised around *Hiriyaru*, the spirits of departed parents. It signifies a remembrance of the parents, thanking them for their care over several years and also entreating them to keep a vigil over the family in future. It is obligatory for all relatives to attend the function, thus renewing kinship relations. *Hiriyaru* worship may be performed twice a year by the 'Kartha'(head) of the family. It normally is held during the Navarathri festival in the first week of November. If this is not possible for some reason, it may also be performed in April–May during the other major festival - Holi. These obviously are not meant to coincide with the dates of the parents' deaths as the Siddhis only observe the first death anniversary. Hindu Siddhis usually have elaborate functions to mark the event, but not so the Christian and Muslim Siddhis.

Language: Siddhis mainly speak the Kannada language, which belongs to the Dravidian family. Some also speak other languages, such as Konkani and Marathi.

Occupation: Almost all Siddhis today subsist as agricultural and casual labourers, contractual or in some cases bonded, some also work as domestic help. The earliest Siddhi settlers who fled Goa and entered the Karnataka forests of North Canara, made the forests their home and started cultivation. In some of the villages in these areas, they form the earliest settlers. The Siddhis of Yellapur are very honest and hard working.

Culture: Siddhis brought to India for sale belonged to many tribes in Ethiopia, Tanzania, Mozambique or Zanzibar, who had their individual customs, traditions, dances, songs, languages and unique techniques. The beginning of their social and cultural decay was their alienation from their tribe, separation in the merchandise ships and severance at the sale as slaves. Such dismantled family could not afford to pass on all that they knew and were following in their homeland. Besides, the masters never created a platform in order to foster the Siddhi culture. Siddhis drum beats had ceased, their singing strangled, their smile forgotten during their slavery in India. The slaves were kept busy and it was natural that the slaves had to learn the master's language be it Portuguese, Kannada, Urdu, Marathi or Konkani, in order to understand their commands and orders. And to be familiar with the people whom they serve they had to familiarize themselves with the local tongues at the expense of their mother tongue. Pinto points out that some of the women as well as men sold self made pickles and for doing this they had to learn the local language, customs of wishing, and ways of dealing with the customers.

Social Status: The autonomy of a social system may either increase or decrease in a changing field, and its expression may be modified. Here the subordinate group does not hold authority over dominant group. Siddhis played important role in various kingdoms such as Bahamani, Bijapur and other kingdoms of the Deccan, initially they attained good reputation in the eyes of locals as people of high rank, caliber, courage and hard work. While Siddhi soldiers served their rulers dutifully the locals were jealous of their loyalty and waited for their downfall. They were slowly recruited for status positions, but their social status declined as the days pushed ahead and Siddhis proved it by their passivity and submission due to helpless circumstances as labourers due to their expulsion from various kingdoms, some sold as slaves where as others yielded to any sort of labour for survival.

Kinship: Kinship outlines a significant component in the whole kinship system as it serves as an indicator to accepting of the kinship relation and patterns of behaviour among various kin groups, where as the family is a social and economic group consisting minimally of one or more parents and their children. Murdock defined the family as a social group characterized by common residence economic cooperation and reproduction. Siddhi families are either joint family, extended or small families. Earlier Siddhis used to live in joint families but now the researcher observed that most of Siddhis follow either extended or micro family system.

Kinship refers to the social recognition and expression of genealogical relationships, both consanguineal and affinal. Palakshappa identified four types of kinship among Siddhis. They are

- **Maneyavaru:** that includes members of a family, which becomes meaningful in the ritual and economic life of these people. All the Maneyavaru belong to a single extended family who trace their relationship to a common ancestor called "*Hiriyaru*". This Maneyavaru generally consists of three generations. The deceased parents of the Ego, his children, his brothers and their off-Springs who fall in the heredity. The beauty of this system is that when a Siddhi household before acquiring a particular implement satisfies itself that other families of the hereditary do not possess it. This is because they share the implements with each other whenever need arises.
- **Bandugalu:** are all the standard paternal kin which is just an expansion of Maneyavaru association. The beauty of this system is, whatever may be the distance between one another, marital relationship is impossible. In this regard the elders of the family have right memory of the lineage and relationship. This is very healthy to the Siddhi community as it does not hamper their health which otherwise can create a number of handicapped (physical and mental) members within the community.
- **Balagadavaru:** covers the maternal kin – the mother's sisters and their children and the mother's brothers and their children.³⁸ The importance of maternal kinship is seen in the observance of rituals and ceremonies as many of the ceremonies require the presence of maternal kin, the uncle be it marriage, initiation, tonsure among Hindus. Among Christians during baptism and marriage while among Muslims during the naming ceremony.
- **Nentaru:** are the newly contracted relations in the course of time, the brothers or sons have migrated to different places in search of the last kinship will become the third kinship i.e., Balagadavaru. Usually the paternal kin are the members of the same settlement except in cases where jobs. The paternal kin come during cultivation.

Family Set up: Family is a place where children establish their first close emotional ties, learn language and begin to internalize cultural norms and values. It is the first unit of socialization. Family among Siddhis is a closer unit than the normal understanding in the locality. The bond is much stronger and the hierarchy in the family much clearer among tribes than outside. Siddhis lack proper social organization hence the family and the settlement form two important aspects of the social organization. Family has always been the corner stone and nucleus of any society or community. Family is the foundational unit of collective organization that addresses and meets the needs of every community member. The life in a settlement has its significance to the family unit. Family in Siddhi community was and is more a social grouping; a recognized institution. It is here where the first phase of enculturation happens and where the morals and fundamental values of Siddhis' life are imparted. Earlier most Siddhi families were characterized by the joint-family system, where by an extended family of parents, grandparents, children and sons' wives occupied the same

living quarters. The eldest male member of the family manages the finances, religious rituals and attends any functions where family representation is required. Their system permitted sale of children as slaves owing to famine, disobedience. But now the Siddhi families are more inclined towards nuclear families. The son, after marriage, is expected to have his own house and earn his living and make his family. Nevertheless joint or extended families are still part of Siddhi community. But education, economic stability and migration for a better living have influenced the life style of Siddhis in the settlements in past two decades. Now the kith and kin gather together for common celebrations such as Hiriyara Puje, marriages, festivals, christening or death in the family though living in the same settlement or migrated to another settlement. The respect and honour that is reserved for the eldest member of the family is preserved when they have such occasions.

Siddhis follow Patriarchal system wherein father is the decision maker. At the same mother is given equal footing in the decision making process. Women command respect and are independent in this tribe than any other in south India. When it comes to managing the household it is the woman that has an upper hand as she contributes to the maintenance of the family in all the ways, be it taking care of the children, farming, working in the field as labourer etc. most significantly both boys and girls are received with equal joy and warmth in the community and have no sex preference when it comes to progeny. An individual is very much emotionally involved in the family that to an extent that breaks down the spatial and temporal barriers between the Siddhis. The obligatory vigour within the family is esteem for seniors and a sense of commitment towards others in community. The relationship beyond the community is also reckoned by the family unit. Siddhi family includes not just the living members but also the dead ancestors. It is commonly believed among Siddhis that spirits are mortal. The life of the deceased remains in the spirit condition until the sins, which one may have committed are washed away by the good deeds of the descendants. The dead can function as “disciplinary agents in helping to mould into socially acceptable behaviour.”The living is obliged to request the supervision of the dead, because the dead have exclusive mission, to conserve the family and divination. It is in this paranormal framework that the Siddhi family operates. Food and lights are offered at least once a year to the ancestors, with rituals in respect and thankfulness to them.

Family Hierarchy: The head of the home is the eldest male member of the family. It can be father in a nuclear family, grandfather in an extended family. Kiran Kamal observes that males in Siddhi community dominate as they are considered to have superior status over women. Ultimate decisions are made by the father or husband that remains final in the family, may it be with regard to betrothal, marriage, education and all other purposes that entail decisions. While in the decision making bodies at the settlements women participate but are not consulted while deciding. The head of the family takes part in meetings of settlements, in which case women who are heads can attend it. But women are highly regarded when it comes to family matters. The headman of the settlement and the eldest son of the family are

both given due respect and a position of honour. They are both addressed as „*jante*” a respectful title in the settlement. Women address their husbands as „*jante*” in order to show their respect and obedience. The ancestral house is called „*devghar* (house of god) and ancestors are revered with respect in this house as mentioned before. The property is divided equally between the male descents either before or after the death of the father. Palakshappa mentions that the widow of the dead has no right to the property of her husband.⁵⁰ The researcher found that there were families where the widows took care of the family and took all the decisions until the eldest son or daughter came of age to do the same. Besides, the children claim ancestral property after the age of eighteen.

Marriage System: Monogamy is the most prevalent form of marital union among the Siddhis. However a few Siddhis were found in polygamous wedlock. Marriages are arranged by the parents. Parallel cousins are avoided in marriage negotiation. Cases of junior levirate and junior sororate were found in Siddhi Society but not in an obligatory form. Divorce is not common among Hindu and Christian Siddhis though there are a few instances, but permitted among the Muslim Siddhis. Widow re-marriage is practiced among Siddhis under any religion. Looking back to Siddhis original culture of the Siddhis, the chief as well as head of a family had many wives and children. Polygamy is pursued in Africa by very many tribes to this day. Besides Islam religion permits a man to have four wives.

Siddhi Sabha: The organization of Siddhis for justice, punishment as well as for taking important decisions is in line with the typical primitive tribes. The settlement forms the ultimate unit of authority and arbitration observes Kiran Kamal Prasad. In every village inhabited by the Siddhi, which is independent in itself, there is a traditional council called *Siddhi Sabha*, who are elected leaders or hold hereditary posts. Palakshappa points out that Sabha which he writes as „*subha*” is a politico-judicial body within a settlement. Siddhi sabha is a settlement body with a domain of its own action and authority. The researcher noticed that the number of leaders for such Sabha varied according to settlements. They are called *jante*, which literally would mean the elders. It is a powerful organ of the social structure among them. It is headed by one, designated as *budwont* (the Wiseman) and assisted by *kolkar* (orderly) or *khajandar* (treasurer). This body ensures the continuity and has the power to dispatch verdicts and punish the guilty or even to excommunicate a person concerned.

Housing: In an interview Delio de Mendonca observed: “The Siddhis in Portuguese India did not have any houses to stay in. They stayed in the quarters underground or the places where the cattle was tied.”⁶⁸ But the Siddhis in the Bijapur kingdom and Hyderabad regions had rather good shelter since they were soldiers and necessary things were provided to them by the royalty.⁶⁹ Compact type of settlement is found among Siddhis. The houses are along both sides of the settlement paths and are constructed in a row along the contours. In some settlements houses are constructed with earthen wall and the inclined roof of which are shaded with reed that is available or grass supported with bamboos. Some houses are

constructed by earthen wall and the wall made of bamboo planks or tree bunches plastered with earth. The huts are shaded with two side inclined thatching instead of four among some Siddhis.

Food Habits: As vagabonds in the forest Siddhis certainly consumed meat that was easily available for their hunting ability. The researcher has personally observed that all Siddhis consume meat at “Siddhi Nyasa” a religious gathering specific to Siddhis alone. The researcher observed that there is a change in their diet. As of now Siddhis diet consists of rice, ragi, maze and other serials. Christian Siddhis occasionally eat meat where as pork is avoided by Muslim Siddhis. Those Siddhis still residing in the forest depend on the roots and fruits collected from the forest besides fish that is available from the rivers and streams. Until strict forest rules were under effect, Siddhis hunted wild boars, wild rabbits, bison, porcupine, birds, wild goat, wild cock and wild buffalos for their diet. They also lived on crabs, tortoise and honey that were easily accessible. “Christian Siddhis use rice for most of the food items because it was their staple food in Africa and other food items such as black millet and wheat are not used much and cereals like horsegram are used to feed the horses and therefore not meant for humans” is their thought. In an interview with Rozai Francis Siddhi of Tatvanigi the researcher learnt that Siddhis of Karwar and Dharwad both have vegetarian and non-vegetarian diet. Hunting has become impossible for Siddhis due to the Wild Life Protection Act. The vegetarian staple food- Jawar, rice and dhal are common to all Siddhi families.

Health: The researcher observed that Most Siddhis enjoyed good health, having good immune system. They are physically tough and rarely fall sick. Their food habits and the herbal medicine keep them far from the doctors and medical practitioners. Siddhis believe that disease comes when they forget their ancestors or when their ancestors are angry with a particular person. Hence the cure is by the ancestors themselves. When a Siddhi in the vicinity gets possessed with the spirit these things are revealed and when appropriate measures are taken to calm the angry ancestors the disease automatically gets cured. The researcher found that such cases seem to be unscientific as there is no proof provided either of the disease or of cure. Dr. Prakash V. Patil in his research on the Biomedical Study of Siddhis of Karnataka found that Siddhi Children showed better nutritional status than the non-Siddhi children where as there was not much significant difference among the adults. He found that lice infection was very less among Siddhis. Scabies, Tinea, Eczema and leprosy were slightly more among the non-Siddhis due to poor personal hygiene.

Medicine: The researcher observed that Chatrangi Beru, Kumpal, Nasari beru, Aupathe Chekke, Sandal wood (paste), Kudi leaves, Bamboo shoots, shoots of few other herbal plants, oil made out of important birds Department of Applied Botany, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri conducted a research into the medical knowledge of the Siddhis and a total of 98 medicinal preparations, involving species of plants, used by the Siddhis of Uttara Kannada in the state of Karnataka were described in this paper based on an ethno medical field study. The finding included 40 hitherto unknown medicinal uses of known medicinal

plants. Among these, the use of the stem sap of *Calamus thwaitesii* as an anti-fertility drug, and the use of the flowers of *Ichnocarpus frutescens* and the rhizome of *Hedychium coronarium* in the treatment of diabetes were noteworthy. The knowledge of medicinal plants of the Siddhis is distinct from that of any other tribes living in the vicinity and animals like peacock, Owl, wild boar, deer, bison and few snakes were used by Siddhis for various cures. Some of the medicinal plants are used in their daily diet keeping them fit.

Language: Siddhis of Karnataka, Maharashtra, Goa, or Gujarat have not retained their ancestral language, Swahili, a language spoken today in Eastern Coast of Africa. The original language of the Siddhis died out. 84 The language which the Siddhis speak is neither Kannada, nor Hindi or Konkani but totally different, a mixture of everything which is very difficult to pick up.

Music: Siddhi's efforts to preserve the culture brought with them from Africa are noteworthy. Their methods, pitch that they employ to sing, songs and the tune employed, their dancing, patting of feet, clapping of hands, and the gross superstitions came straight from Africa. Despite banning Siddhis from using drums, dancing, singing during their slavery the culture has sustained the test of time. Music is used with almost every human activity and had a persistent central role in African culture. Moreover it is generally believed that music has an affective power and functions as a force or causal agent. "The gods will not descend without song" is a common aphorism in West African cultures observes Olly Wilson. Besides music is integrally related to language, because at the root level both are modes of communication that use sound and language exist in time. Siddhis love music which is noticed even in their language as they drag a bit with a musical flow. The incorporation of body motion as an integral part of the music-making process is essential to Siddhis. Body motion and music are integral components of the same process as we witness singing and playing music is associated with elaborate body movements among Siddhis.

Songs : Poogdi dance is mere a dance of attractive and collective movements. The songs sung for this dance are sometimes composed spontaneously according to the mood of the community. The *sigmu* and *dhamaam* songs are simple comments on life with some religious references. However, it is customary in *sigmu* dance to begin this dance with the formula for making the sign of the cross. The songs followed can be of humour, telling a small story, or anything in reference to Siddhi way of life such as hunting and fishing.

Dances: Siddhis have an almost instinctive flair for music, an emotional product, developed, through suffering. They have their own traditional musical instrument a long kind of narrow drum of various sizes, from two to eight feet in length, three or four of which make a band. The principal dancers or leaders are dressed in a variety of wild and savage fashions, always ornamented with a number of tails of the smaller wild animals. In Africa, the drum is a language organized into a discourse: there are orchestral groups of drums where each instrument has its voice. The drum is an act of sharing ... Dances are performed on festive

occasions such as marriage, the birth of a child, feasts of a saint, and funerals. Dhamaam dance is a mark of Siddhi identity in the Western Ghats. Dhamaam dance is performed on *navarathri* as well as on *hiriyara puje* and other entertaining occasions exhibiting their distinctiveness. While a man plays dhamaam at the background, two ladies or two men wearing sarees with peacock feathers and a coconut in another hand dance to the rhythm that is unique.

Siddhi Culture: Man cannot control culture i.e., beliefs, customs, institution, languages, tools, techniques, dwellings or art forms. Culture controls man, man can merely react to it. Culture is the independent variant and man is dependent variable. Siddhis in Karwar and Dharwad districts of Karnataka have their culture exclusive to them. Since the time they have entered India as merchants, soldiers, slaves, rulers or artists they have tried to retain their rich culture. Yet some of them could not retain them due to *sits-in-leben* or ground realities that forced Siddhis to integrate things from the locals besides making their own contribution to the local cultures. This chapter deals with various aspects of Siddhis culture and practices that are observed by the researcher, their customs, traditions, and other cultural elements specific to Siddhis.

4.PROBLEMS OF SIDDHIS

Illiteracy, poverty and oppression by the landlords and exploitation of Siddhis as cheap labourers are the focal barriers for their upliftment. Lack of willingness and fear of failure haunts them from getting out of their backwardness. Opposition from the dominant locals is another factor adding to all these woes. Siddhis are highly influenced by Havak Brahmins as they have a master and servant association. Siddhis, who were well built, healthy for manual labour, did not hold any land rather always worked under someone else. One of the techniques of making them subservient was to falsely accuse a Siddhi of theft or other crimes which they would accept it in their innocence and fear. Then try them in the village Panchayat. No Siddhi knew the rules and regulations while they were tried at Katte (Village Panchayat System). One who frees him is considered a saviour and the freed Siddhi would be subservient for life.

Influence of modernization: The researcher noticed that there is a gradual change in the type of settlement they are living in and this could be due to modernization, urbanization, and industrialization. The modernization has influenced them when it comes to housing and organizing the settlements. There has been drainages layed while the houses are rebuilt in symmetrical rows or streets. The settlements seem to have minimum of two streets which is divided by a 8-10 feet road. The houses are built using cement and burnt bricks or at least plastered with cement outside in order to prevent the house from falling due to heavy and incessant rains. The thatched roofs in some settlements are replaced with tiles under which most of the old generation is not happy nevertheless live in fear of damage that could cause if it collapses. When it comes to the living style the influence of industrialization is noticed.

Most of the siddhi youth work outside their settlements and when they come home they bring materials that are not seen before by the residents of settlements. The youth influenced by the industrialization insist on usage of machinery for agriculture though most of them cannot afford. But for sure the youth are aware of the use of machinery which eases their work load.

5.CONCLUSION

Social conditions of Siddhis in the Karwar and Dharwad districts of Karnataka are yet to see the light of development though they enjoy the status of Schedule Tribe since 2003. In this bargain, though Siddhis might lose certain traditional, cultural, communitarian richness carried down the ages by their ancestors, nevertheless, the social condition of this tribe is pitiable and needs emancipation from their poverty, illiteracy and social discrimination in order to give them their deserved dignity. The subservient condition of these Siddhis has pushed them down to the lowest strata of the society where they have fewer opportunities to rise above their discriminations and oppressions. Their social condition has not changed much from their slavery to freedom. Their only consolation was to be free to live an isolated life undisturbed by the external forces. But this scenario is slowly changing as the neighbourhood is interfering in their social functioning and way of life. Siddhis have had limited options for action and yet they have survived despite the odds. One reason that keeps them survive the test of time is their ability to adapt, flexibility, improvisation in their strategies and tactics to acclimatize to new environments.

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